

Quality of life of selected psychology students at this time of pandemic

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess the quality of life of selected Psychology students of St. Dominic College of Asia. A total of 124 Psychology students participated in the study. The study utilized a 26-item World Health Organization Quality of Life Scale which measures four dimensions such as Physical Health, Psychological, Social Relationships, and Environment. Results show that respondents have a high physical health dimension, high psychological dimension, high social relationships, and high environmental dimension. The study run test for significant difference for both sex at birth demographic profile and year level. Across four dimensions of quality of life, the computed p-value for sex at birth and year level is greater than .05 alpha level. Hence, there is no significant difference and null hypothesis is accepted.

Keywords: Quality of life; Psychology students; Pandemic.

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Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), quality of life is an individual's perception of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live (WHO, 1996). It requires an evaluation of an individual's negative and positive aspects of life. The quality of life is divided into four (4) domains namely: physical health, psychological, social relationships, and environmental.

The physical health domain includes activities of daily living, dependence on medicinal substances and medical aids, energy and fatigue, mobility, pain and discomfort, sleep and rest, and work capacity. The psychological domain refers to body image and appearance, negative and positive feelings, self-esteem, spirituality / religion / personal beliefs, thinking, learning, memory and concentration. Social relationships domain refers to personal relationships, social support and sexual activity. Lastly, environment domain refers to financial resources, freedom, physical safety and security, health and social care, home environment, opportunities for acquiring new information and skills, participation in and opportunities for recreation or leisure activities, physical environment and transport (Kirchengast & Haslinger, 2008; Lee et al., 2020).

Quality of Life measurements are indicative of emotional well-being which can help gauge on the factors affecting a student's academic performance (Huang et al., 2017). This means that emotional well-being may be a factor that affects an individual's quality of life and academic performance. However, QoL is much more than happiness and life satisfaction, it is a multidimension scale that includes physical, psychological, environmental, and social domains (Ruggeri et al., 2020).

This study aimed to assess the quality of life of selected Psychology students of St. Dominic College of Asia. This study assumes that there is no significant relationship with any of the QoL domains of the students during pandemic.

Methodology

The researchers utilized the descriptive-quantitative research wherein data is collected and statistically analyzed using SPSS. The researchers used the WHOQoL – BREF which is an abbreviated form of the Quality of Life Scale Instrument developed by the World Health Organization (Vahedi, 2010; WHO, 1996). This instrument has a total of 26 items, each scored from 1 to 5 and comprising four (4) domains. The scores were then added within each domain.

The physical health domain includes seven (7) items measuring mobility, daily activities, functional capacity, energy, pain, and sleep. Six (6) items were included to measure psychological health while three (3) items are for social health. Eight items focusing on environmental domain were also included.

Due to the limitations brought upon by the COVID-19 pandemic, the researchers opted to convert the WHOQoL – BREF to an online survey via Google Forms and was disseminated to the respondents via Blackboard, email, and group chats. All data was handled with confidentiality.

The Quality of Life Scale was originally created by John Flanagan and has been adapted for use in chronic illness groups. According to Burckhardt & Anderson (2003), no other QoL scale has been created that has extensive attention to diversity and individual perspective.

Results and Analysis

Table 1
Demographic profile of the respondents

Demographic Profile		Frequency	Percent
Sex at Birth	Male	22	18
	Female	102	82
	Total	124	100
Year Level	First	34	27
	Second	33	27
	Third	28	23
	Fourth	29	23
	Total	124	100

Table 1 shows that there are more female respondents (82%) than male respondents (18%) for this study. A total of 124 psychology students from first year to fourth year level participated.

Table 2
Mean score for physical health dimension of Quality of Life Scale per demographic profile

Demographic Profile		Mean	SD	Interpretation
Sex at Birth	Male	49.73	16.13	High
	Female	47.09	15.72	Low
	Total	47.55	15.75	High
Year Level	First	48.29	16.67	High
	Second	47.33	14.26	Low
	Third	47.32	13.10	Low
	Fourth	47.14	19.09	Low
	Total	47.55	15.76	High

On the above table, the results show that the male respondents obtained a mean score of 49.73 which indicates high physical quality of life, while the female respondents obtained a mean score of 47.09 which indicates a low physical quality of life. For the year level, only the first year respondents yielded a high interpretation of the physical domain of quality of life.

Gender differences in terms of physical health impacts the QoL of the respondents. Gender stereotypes, sexuality, and body image makes female susceptible to view their physical aspect negatively than males. The overall physical dimension of the quality of life of the respondents is 47.55, which is on the high scale.

Table 3
Mean score for psychological health dimension of Quality of Life Scale per demographic profile

Demographic Profile		Mean	SD	Interpretation
Sex at Birth	Male	50.73	25.26	High
	Female	45.80	18.89	Low
	Total	46.68	20.14	High
Year Level	First	47.88	22.99	High
	Second	44.21	20.75	Low
	Third	45.21	16.54	Low
	Fourth	49.48	19.57	High
	Total	46.68	20.14	High

The results show that the male respondents obtained a mean score of 50.73 which indicates high psychological quality of life, while the female respondents obtained a mean score of 45.80 which indicates a low psychological quality of life. In terms of year level, the first year and fourth year respondents obtained a high psychological quality of life with a mean score of 47.88 and 49.48, respectively while the second and third year respondents obtained mean scores of 44.21 and 45.21, respectively which indicates a low psychological quality of life.

The overall psychological dimension of the quality of life of the respondents is 46.68 which indicates that the students have low levels of QoL. This result is concurrent with the findings of Bonsaksen (2012). His study on gender differences in quality of life showed that women tend to be more vulnerable to depression than male. Social constructionist approach states that gender differences in mental health are actively produced and reproduced by social interactions.

Table 4
Mean score for social relationship dimension of Quality of Life Scale per demographic profile

Demographic Profile		Mean	SD	Interpretation
Sex at Birth	Male	43.18	23.04	Low
	Female	47.25	18.99	High
	Total	46.52	19.73	High
Year Level	First	48.00	20.29	High
	Second	42.97	20.72	Low
	Third	47.79	13.81	High
	Fourth	47.62	23.00	High
	Total	46.52	19.73	High

The results show that the male respondents obtained a mean score of 43.18, which indicates low social relationships quality of life, while the female respondents obtained a mean score of 47.25 which indicates a high social relationships quality of life. In terms of year level, the second year respondents obtained a low social relationship quality of life with a mean score of 42.97, while the first, third and fourth year respondents obtained a mean score of 48, 47.79 and 47.72, respectively, indicating a high social relationship quality of life.

The overall social relationships dimension of the quality of life of the respondents is 46.52 which falls on the low level. This result shows that female students tend to communicate more and interact than their male counterparts. According to Kendall and Tannen (2015), communication styles also differ between genders.

Table 5
Mean score for environmental dimension of Quality of Life Scale per demographic profile

Demographic Profile		Mean	SD	Interpretation
Sex at Birth	Male	58.64	15.35	High
	Female	56.61	14.36	Low
	Total	56.97	14.50	High
Year Level	First	57.29	15.90	High
	Second	54.54	14.88	Low
	Third	56.57	13.01	Low
	Fourth	59.38	14.04	High
	Total	56.97	14.50	High

The results show that the male respondents obtained a mean score of 58.64 which indicates high environmental dimension quality of life, while the female respondents obtained a mean score of 56.61 which indicates a low environmental dimension quality of life. In terms of year level, the first and fourth year respondents obtained a high environmental dimension of quality of life with a mean score of 57.29 and 59.38, respectively. On the other hand, the second and third year respondents obtained a mean score of 54.55 and 56.57, respectively, which indicates a low environmental quality of life. The overall environmental dimension of the quality of life of the respondents is 56.97.

Table 6
Test for significant difference

Demographic Profile	Dimension of Quality of Life	p-value	Significance	Ho Decision
Sex at Birth	Physical Health	0.488	Not Significant	Accept
	Psychological	0.396	Not Significant	Accept
	Social Relationships	0.446	Not Significant	Accept
	Environmental	0.574	Not Significant	Accept
Year Level	Physical Health	0.991	Not Significant	Accept
	Psychological	0.727	Not Significant	Accept
	Social Relationships	0.695	Not Significant	Accept
	Environmental	0.677	Not Significant	Accept

*Significant at .05 alpha level

The results showed that the computed p-value is greater than the alpha level of .05 which shows that there is no significant relationship, and the null hypothesis is accepted across all demographic profiles and dimensions of the quality of life.

Discussion and Conclusions

There are more female psychology students, who participated in the study. First year and second year students dominated as respondents in the study.

In terms of physical health, it is noted that female psychology students, second to fourth year students have low physical health quality of life. Physical health is important because it can contribute to the academic welfare of the students and can increase positive mental conditioning. Gender differences in physical health may be attributed to a person's body image and experience in terms of gender stereotypes.

In terms of psychological dimension, it is noted that female psychology students, second to third year students have low psychological quality of life. Thinking ability is important to students, therefore, in the absence of a balanced psychological welfare, it can contribute to how students will respond and think positively in terms of their academics. Recent trends in psychology support this result as gender gap in mental health still exists. According to Al Dhaheri et al. (2021), some studies have found that hormonal changes and psychosocial factors may play a significant role in women's psychological health.

In terms of social relationships, it is noted that male psychology students and second year psychology students have low social relationships. Social relationship is important because it can contribute to the overall welfare of the students in terms of socialization and active participation. Gender differences are present in social interaction. For instance, females tend to communicate more often in details than their male counterparts.

For environmental dimension, female psychology students and second year psychology students have low environmental dimension. It is very important to check the environment where the students are since at this time of pandemic, students are working online at home.

After analysis of data and results, the researchers recommend the following:

- Create programs that will increase students' involvement in terms of physical health since physical welfare is important and crucial if left unaided or unresolved.
- Come up with an intervention program to promote mental health, by the Guidance Office in coordination with the Department of Psychology.
- Be more visible to increase socialization and participation of students in student activities.
- Increase student consultation in terms of online engagement with their respective courses, to increase capacity building in academics and learning within their own home.

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